

FATIGUE PERFORMANCE OF MODERN SUBMERGED ARC WELDS IN 85MM GRADE S355 STEEL

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The fatigue design documents BS 7608 and DNV RP C203, include a ‘thickness correction’ which reduces the design S-N curve for components thicker than the reference value. Wind turbine structures use very large plate thicknesses ($\gg 50\text{mm}$) with fatigue-critical circumferential welds made with submerged arc welding (SAW). There is concern in the industry that the thickness correction included in the fatigue design standards are overly conservative. This paper presents results of recent fatigue tests on SAW welds in 85mm thick grade S355 steel, allowing the suitability of the thickness correction to be investigated. The results suggest that a thickness exponent of 0.125 may be more suitable for modern SAW welds in thick S355 steel.

Keywords: Submerged arc welds, thickness correction, fatigue, SN curves.

INTRODUCTION

In a wind turbine structure, the foundation, tower and transition piece support the nacelle and rotor. Turbine sizes, particularly in offshore wind farms, are increasing and so the foundations, transition pieces and towers are correspondingly increasing in size. Monopile foundations, transition pieces and towers are fabricated from thick plates which are rolled into cans and welded together. The plates used to manufacture monopiles and towers is very thick with thickness of 80 and 100mm not uncommon.

Offshore wind structures experience cyclic loading, and the circumferential welds in the monopiles, towers and transition pieces are fatigue critical details. Designers of these structures use fatigue design documents, such as BS 7608 [1] and DNV RP C203 [2] to calculate expected fatigue performance.

The thickness correction is commonly applied to reduce the design S-N curve for welds in components thicker than the reference value. It modifies the stress range used to calculate the expected fatigue life and takes the form:

$$S = S_B \left(\frac{t_{ref}}{t} \right)^b \quad (1)$$

S_B is the stress range from the standard SN curve, “ t ” is the thickness in the component of interest, t_{ref} is the thickness associated with the standard SN curve, and b is the exponent. In [1], the exponent is 0.25 and the reference thickness is 25mm for welds other than those in tubular joints. In [2], t_{ref} is 25mm and b varies between 0.25 and 0.05, depending on the weld class.

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The thickness correction reduces the fatigue life calculated for welds in plates larger than the reference thickness, and so is effectively a thickness penalty.

The circumferential welds used to join the cans that make up a wind turbine tower or monopole are usually made by submerged arc welding (SAW) because SAW is a high productivity welding process. The welds are made from both sides of the plate. When the operational cyclic stresses are perpendicular to the weld, as they are on the circumferential welds in a wind turbine structure, and when the weld cap is intact (Figure 1), these welds are a Class D detail in [1] and [2].

FIGURE 1 A butt weld made from both sides is a Class D weld detail.

Applying the thickness correction to a circumferential weld in 85mm thick steel, using an exponent of 0.25, produces a thickness correction factor of 0.74. Given that the equation of an SN curve is $N=CS^{-3}$, and fatigue life depends on stress range raised to the power -3, the fatigue life is reduced by a factor of 2.5. To account for this reduction in fatigue life, designers of wind turbine structures increase the structure's thickness to reduce the stress ranges experienced by the welds, allowing the required design fatigue life to be obtained.

There is concern in the industry that this thickness penalty is too severe. If a lower thickness penalty could be justified for the plate thicknesses used in wind turbine structures, the benefits to the wind industry would be significant. With a lower reduction in fatigue life, the thickness of plate specified by designers for wind structures could be reduced. Given that each wind farm is made up of 10's of wind turbines, and each structure is several meters in diameter and 50+m high, this would save a significant quantity of steel, and this potential for reducing the quantity of steel needed in these structures has motivated researchers to look again at the thickness correction. Researchers have reported either no or a lower effect than recommended in current standards of thickness on the fatigue performance of as-welded butt welds (Drebenstedt and Hofmann [3] and Pedersen [4]).

The thickness correction that is in the current edition of [1] was first published in the UK Department of Energy guidance note for offshore installations, Department of Energy [5]. The exponent of the thickness correction published in that guidance note was 0.25. The exponent was derived by comparing fatigue test results from welds in transverse K butt welds tested under axial loading and transverse non-load carrying fillet welds tested under both axial and bending loads, i.e. cruciform joints, in which the thickness of the load carrying plate was between 10 and 25mm, with the majority of the results from specimens with a main plate thickness of 13mm. For each plate thickness, the mean SN curve was obtained by regression analysis, and the fatigue strength at 1E5 cycles and 2E6 cycles was calculated. This was plotted against plate thickness, on double logarithmic axes, and regression analysis was again carried out to obtain the slope of these curves. This slope corresponded to the exponent in the thickness correction factor. The slopes ranged from 0.075 to 0.4. As subsequently explained by Gurney [6], the data was considered and it was decided to use a reference thickness of 25mm rather than 13mm, because the thickness penalty with a reference thickness of 13mm would be too severe, and an exponent of 0.25 was chosen as a 'reasonable approximation to the available data'.

As explained by Lotsberg [7], the thickness effect is a geometrical effect. The stress gradient through the plate thickness is steeper at the toe of the weld in a thin plate compared to that in a thick

plate under the same applied stress. For the same initial flaw size at the weld toe, the stress at the tip of the initiating flaw is therefore lower in thinner plate (Figure 2). This lower stress results in a lower initial fatigue crack growth rate, and so a larger number of cycles to crack initiation, and a longer overall fatigue life. Or conversely, the effect produces a shorter fatigue life of the weld in the thicker plate. The effect is more pronounced under bending stresses because the stress gradient is larger.

The 2014 current edition of [1], actually provides a ‘bending and thickness’ correction factor, which accounts for the larger effect of thickness when the applied load is in bending. This was developed after further analysis of the fatigue performance of cruciform joints by Sun [8]. As shown in equations 2 and 3, without any bending stresses, the standard thickness correction applies. When bending is present, the stress range is reduced more.

$$S = S_B \left(\frac{t_{ref}}{t} \right)^b [1 + 0.18\Omega^{1.4}] \tag{2}$$

and

$$\Omega = \frac{\Delta\sigma_b}{\Delta\sigma_b + \Delta\sigma_m} \tag{3}$$

Where $\Delta\sigma_b$ and $\Delta\sigma_m$ are the bending and membrane stress ranges, respectively.

FIGURE 2 Illustration of the of the geometrical thickness effect (the stress on the Upper and Lower surfaces are the same but $T > t$ and so $S_t < S_T$ at the tip of a flaw).

Fillet welds belong to a lower fatigue class than butt welds because the steeper weld angle the toe of a fillet weld results in a larger stress concentration than that at the toe of a butt weld. For a given applied stress, the larger stress concentration factor at the toe of a fillet weld would therefore result in a larger surface stress and therefore a higher stress at a flaw at the weld toe, with a higher fatigue crack growth rate and so shorter life. A larger effect of plate thickness would therefore be expected for a fillet weld than a butt weld. To account for this, [2] provides different thickness exponents for different Classes. It is 0.25 for Class F and below, matching [1]. For the higher fatigue Classes, it is 0.2 for Class E and D, 0.15 for Class C2, 0.1 for Class C1, 0.05 for Class C and 0 for Classes B1 and B2.

FIGURE 3 Illustration of the enhanced thickness effect demonstrated by a fillet weld compared to a butt welds ($S_{UF} > S_{UB}$, and so $S_F > S_B$ for a given flaw size, plate thickness and applied load).

Fatigue testing of very thick specimens under axial loading requires a high load capacity test machine. These are relatively uncommon and so there is therefore little fatigue test data available from fatigue tests on butt welds in very thick plate (>60mm) reported in the literature.

This paper presents results of recent fatigue tests on SAW welds in 85mm thick grade S355 steel, and investigates the suitability of the thickness correction exponent.

Materials and methods

The SAW welds were fabricated as part of the ‘Rapidweld’ project, whose main aim was to investigate the use of electron beam (EB) welding to produce longitudinal welds in wind turbine structures, Johnston et al [9].

The specimens in question were fabricated to investigate the fatigue performance of the intersection of a SAW weld with an EB weld. The SAW welds joined unwelded 85mm thick, grade S355ML plate to 85mm thick, grade S355ML plate containing an EB weld representing the longitudinal weld in a monopile. The SAW welds were fabricated by Sif, a world-leading monopile manufacturer, using a production welding procedure used for the manufacture of wind turbine monopiles. The welds were made from two sides and the caps were remained as-welded. They met the acceptance criteria of ISO 5817 level B, [10]. The weld angle was 150 degrees, and so the welds all had very good profiles. Non-destructive examination (NDE) was performed and no unacceptable flaws were present.

Waisted fatigue test specimens were waterjet cut from the welded plates, with the SAW weld transverse to the specimen length. Specimens were finish machined to size by CNC machining. The final specimen dimensions are shown in Figure 4. The edges were polished and corners radiused to limit the likelihood that fatigue cracking would initiate from those locations.

FIGURE 4 Dimensions of the fatigue test specimens (not to scale).

Strain gauges were used to monitor the stress ranges applied during testing so that any additional stresses due to bending caused by misalignment of the specimens at the SAW weld could be measured and included in the reported nominal stress range.

The fatigue tests were conducted at TWI, in air, at room temperature in servohydraulic test machines, under load control. Specimens were tested under constant amplitude cyclic loading in tension, with a high maximum stress to mimic the effect of high tensile residual stresses present in welds in the full components. The stress range cycled down from a maximum stress of 277MPa (the actual yield strength of the S355 plate was measured to be only 346MPa, and this corresponded to 80% of the minimum measured yield stress). The minimum stress was varied to enable the specimens to be tested at different stress ranges.

Tests were run until the machine displacement exceeded a set value, to reduce the likelihood of damage to the test machine at the high forces employed. This resulting fatigue crack lengths were approximately half of the specimen thickness. The remaining fatigue life compared to the fatigue life to a half-thickness crack is considered negligible. Six specimens were tested.

Results

In all six specimens, the fatigue crack initiated at the weld toe of the SAW weld. The results are summarised in Table 1. There were an equal number of cracks that initiated on the plain side and the EB weld side of the SAW weld, indicating that the EB weld did not affect the fatigue performance of the SAW weld. Figure 5 shows a side view of a cracked specimen, and the weld toe at which the crack initiated is arrowed. As can be seen, the weld profile is very smooth, and the weld toe angle is shallow and so there was a low stress concentration associated with the butt welds.

TABLE 1 Summary of fatigue test results

Specimen code	Nominal stress range at crack location, MPa	Endurance, cycles	Comments
W10	152	549,923	Cracked at SAW weld toe on both sides
W11	226	274,671	Cracked at SAW weld toe on plain side
W12	224	434,202	Cracked at SAW weld toe on plain side
W13	186	332,836	Cracked at SAW weld toe on both sides
W14	211	238,865	Cracked at SAW weld toe on EB weld side
W15	194	148,807	Cracked at SAW weld toe on EB weld side

FIGURE 5 Side view of weld W12, that cracked on the plain side of the SAW weld. The crack initiated at the SAW weld toe.

Analysis

The mean of the results was obtained by standard regression analysis. With a forced slope of $m = 3$, to enable more straightforward comparison of the results with standard SN curves, the intercept ($\log C$) of the mean of the test results was 12.3659 and the standard deviation of $\log N$ (SD) was 0.218. This is similar to the expected SD for welded joints, which is 0.2 in [2], adding more evidence that the presence of the EB weld did not affect the performance of the SAW welds.

The mean curve was compared to the [2] Class D mean and design SN curves, with and without the thickness correction. [2] provides only design curves. The mean Class D SN curve was calculated using an intercept located 2SD above the design curve, ie $12.164 + 0.4 = 12.564$.

It can be seen in Figure 6 that the uncorrected Class D mean curve is much higher than that of the test results. The Class D thickness correction in [2] of $(25/85)^{0.2}$ was applied and the standard thickness corrected Class D curve is much lower than that of the test results. A thickness correction is therefore needed, but the current recommendation is too onerous for these results.

The thickness correction factor needed to make the mean of the test results match the thickness corrected DNV Class D mean requires an exponent of 0.125 (i.e. a thickness correction factor of $(25/85)^{0.125}$). This is close to the thickness correction factor recommended in [2] for the Class C1 curve, where the exponent is 0.1.

Applying this new thickness correction places the mean of the thickness corrected Class D mean curve coincident with the mean curve of the test results, and the thickness corrected Class D design curve is just below the lowest test result (Figure 7).

FIGURE 6 Test results plotted on an SN curve with test results mean curve. Included are the mean and design curves, with and without the standard thickness correction, from [2].

FIGURE 7 Test results plotted on an SN curve with test results mean curve and the Class D mean and design curves using a thickness correction with an exponent of 0.125.

Conclusion

The results suggest that the current recommendation of an exponent equal to 0.25 (in [1]) or 0.2 (in [2]) reduce the calculated fatigue life too much for SAW welds in thick plate subjected to axial loading. This is because the thickness correction recommended in standards were obtained from analysis of cruciform joints, which have high stress concentrations at the weld toe, and so experience a larger effect of differences in thickness than modern butt welds used in wind turbine structures. These have smooth weld profiles and so much lower stress concentrations.

Although the dataset is small, the results suggest a thickness exponent of 0.125 is more suitable for modern as-welded SAW welds in 85mm thick grade S355 steel subjected to axial loading. With an exponent of 0.125, fatigue life of a weld in 85mm plate would only be reduced by a factor of 1.6, compared to 2.5 using the exponent of 0.25 allowing steel thicknesses to be reduced by designers, and subsequent material and cost savings.

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LIST OF SYMBOLS

S	Stress range
S_B	Stress range from the standard SN curve
T	Thickness in the component of interest,
t_{ref}	Thickness associated with the standard SN curve
b	Exponent of the thickness correction
N	Fatigue endurance (= fatigue life)
C	Constant of the S-N curve
m	Slope of the SN curve
Ω	Bending correction factor
$\Delta\sigma_b$	Bending stress range
$\Delta\sigma_m$	Membrane stress range

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